

MetaDocencia Authorship Guidelines

Emmanuel Iarussi, Eunice Mercado Lara, Iván Poggio, Laura Ación, Laura Ascenzi, Malvika Sharan, Nicolás Palopoli, Paola Lefer, Romina Pendino, Verónica Xhardez

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Overview

This document provides a set of guidelines on how to give proper credit and show recognition for contributions to outputs of work performed by MetaDocencia team members following MetaDocencia's [core values](#), especially those of integrity, autonomy, inclusion and community. These guidelines are part of our editorial policy, based on the principle of openness, that promotes equality of opportunities and the integration of multiple voices in the production of scientific and institutional publications.

In a nutshell

- All persons who contribute to MetaDocencia's outputs should be fairly credited for their contribution.
- As a general rule, MetaDocencia is generous in granting authorship.
- These guidelines help MetaDocencia team members recognize situations that merit authorship, including for different types of roles.
- These guidelines also facilitate procedures for the resolution of conflicts around authorship.

Background and approach

All persons who contribute to MetaDocencia (MD), including those in the Executive Team, the Advisory Committee, the coordinating team, the working groups, external collaborators, and others eventually involved in MetaDocencia activities, are expected to perform their activities according to our [Community Guidelines](#).

In the spirit of this agreement, MD community members are expected to give and receive fair credit for any work performed. This ranges from contributions made

solely by a person to participation in projects involving collaborations among partners with experience in different disciplines.

As a general principle, we should fairly acknowledge contributions of different types and from different disciplines, and credit each contribution as authorship.

General procedure

Every MD community member is invited to claim, request or suggest authorship for materials they have contributed to, such as documentation of procedures, white papers, training materials, academic publications and institutional reports, following the guidelines and procedures expressed herein.

MetaDocencia is committed to actively following this policy to acknowledge and recognize the work of their community members.¹

Credit authorship

Any person who made any contribution towards a project developed by MetaDocencia, regardless of their role and engagement status with our community, should be listed as an author or co-author of any output from the project.

We follow an editorial policy based on principles of Open Science, that recognizes all contributions to the documentation of research, academic and institutional procedures publicly, and includes those steps taken to make them more findable, reproducible, and accessible (in compliance with [MetaDocencia's accessibility policy](#)).

The following represents situations in which MetaDocencia must credit contributors of a written document as authors. The specific contributions to be considered as authorship include:

¹ We suggest referring to The Turing Way's book chapter on [Authorship and contributions on academic articles](#) for background on traditional authorship, different kinds of recognition, and acknowledgement of contributors.

- Participation in the creation of guidelines, guides, policies, reports, surveys, journal manuscripts, and any other documents developed by MetaDocencia;
- Contributions to a project in supporting roles such as proof-reading, revision of materials or translations;
- Conceptualization, writing, or revision of blog posts;
- Obtention, wrangling, and analysis of data;
- Coding of software to obtain, wrangle, or analyze data;
- Preparation of technical reports based on the analysis of data.

MetaDocencia will seek approval before publishing names, affiliations and other public information of authors on any side products of the work, such as website pages, slides in presentations, and reports.

Whenever possible, MetaDocencia will upload materials to Zenodo (following our [Guide to Zenodo](#)) and add ORCID IDs from each author (e.g. [facilitated by our ORCID profile setup guide](#)).

Claim authorship

Authors need to give explicit approval before being listed as authors. The procedure for gathering authorship should start as soon as a project's output is started, meaning when a manuscript draft is created, to give the opportunity for true consent and participation. Project outputs that require authorship will be circulated no later than 15 calendar days before the expected publication date to ask for additional authorship requests and approval. Updates to the original authors' list will remain open until the moment the output is published. Corrections after the publication date will also be accepted. Updates to the originally published material will also be open to accept additional authors.

It is acceptable for a person to include their name and details among the authors of the output. Another person may include contributors' names among the authors, however, should ask for approval before including them as authors.

If for any reason a contributor is unacknowledged as author, or is included but disagrees with authorship order, or is required to account for aspects of an output that they were not responsible for, they can request a restorative action on the basis of the Managing Conflict section below.

Fair authorship

When participating in a collaboration, MD community members who participate in the project should be invited to co-author publications generated by the project. The author's role should be discussed upon invitation. MD community members will commit to fulfilling all co-authoring responsibilities that have been previously agreed with collaborators, with the highest international standards.

While contributions such as those listed in the sections above merit authorship, there are times when fair recognition requires the assignment of roles selected from a broad range of well-defined contribution types. A formal definition of these roles, in the form of a high-level taxonomy of terms, is given by the widely adopted [CRedit](#) (Contributor Roles Taxonomy system). When a formal assignment of authorship roles is needed please use of the [CRedit](#) taxonomy of contributor roles to provide details on the participation of each author. An [extended version](#) of this system that recognizes differences between contributorship and authorship roles was prepared by Malvika Sharan and is available from the Open Research Community Management at The Alan Turing Institute. We suggest following this system for a standardized definition of author/contributor roles to set individual expectations, reach collective agreements, and provide fair recognition linked to project outputs.

We recognize that in certain disciplines and circumstances, the order of the authors is significant and could make a difference. In those cases, we suggest that authors decide on the order based on their fair understanding of each other's contribution to the output, and requesting the help of an Executive Director if needed. When the contribution of two or more persons is deemed similar enough that no distinction about the relevance of their contributions can be made, it is acceptable to give more preeminent roles to those persons who may benefit more from that in the short term.

Managing Conflict

A request to address a conflict regarding authorship arises when an MD community member identifies a situation that goes against these guidelines and decides to contact members of the MD Executive team or Community Guidelines team about it.

The Community Guidelines team acts as the first point of contact. It should be notified of authorship conflicts by email to pdcc@metadocencia.org. In the event that any other team member is informed of an authorship conflict, they should notify the Community Guidelines team for its treatment.

In general, the Community Guidelines team will address the issue according to its usual [procedures \(defined in Spanish\)](#), following a restorative logic that allows to take remedial steps towards an equitable resolution and subsequent learning so that the situation is not repeated.

The Community Guidelines team will always notify the Advisory Committee Chair (ACC) about the situation upon becoming aware and could seek the ACC's support on how to handle it. If the ACC is involved in the authorship conflict, the Community Guidelines team will notify the other person in the Executive Team. If this is not appropriate, then any other Advisory Committee member will be notified.

If it is decided that the situation should be discussed in the Advisory Committee, an extraordinary meeting will be convened to deliberate on it as soon as possible, in accordance with MetaDocencia's governance values and principles. The meeting will be open to all MD team members and the resolution will be communicated to the whole team.

References

MetaDocencia is thankful to the persons and organizations that authored the following resources, which served as inspiration for this document:

1. How we credit contributions in the CSCCE community.
<https://www.cscce.org/how-we-credit-contributions-in-the-cscce-community/>
2. A simpler way to submit to eLife.
https://elifesciences.org/inside-elife/13f2ccb2/for-authors-a-simpler-way-to-submit-to-elife?gclid=CjwKCAjwgZCoBhBnEiwAz35RwnoUjrjchL0sgzRa61zZSk2pf8UIVuzmNXDSU0tuyVQxp6BRoFug5xoCUy0QAvD_BwE
3. Academic Authorship.
<https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/communication/aa.html>
4. Enabling the Contributor Roles Taxonomy for author contributions.
<https://elifesciences.org/inside-elife/f39cfcf5/enabling-the-contributor-roles-taxonomy-for-author-contributions>
5. FORRT on Authorship.
<https://forrt.org/glossary/authorship/>
6. Zenodo FAIR principles.
<https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

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